

NEUROFIBRES

D 8.1 Website and logo for *Neurofibres*

H2020 – FET PROACTIVE – 01 - 2016

Project N° 732344

WP Leader: **SESCAM**

Due date of deliverable: **28/02/2017 (M2)**

Actual submission date: **Month 2**

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement No 732344.

Neurofibres consortium

- Servicio de Salud de Castilla La Mancha (SESCAM)
- The Chancellor, Masters and Scholars of the University of Cambridge (UCAM)
- Axon Cable (AXON' CABLE)
- Università Degli Studi di Trento (UNITN)
- Kungliga Tekniska Högskolan (KTH)
- Université D'aix Marseille (AMU)
- Universität des Saarlandes (USAAR)

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Document control

Title	D 8.1 Website and logo for <i>Neurofibres</i>
Contributing work package	WP 8: Activities for the exploitation, dissemination and communication of results
Actual delivery date	28/02/2017
Dissemination level	PUBLIC
Contributors	SESCAM

Revision history

Version	Date	Authors	Description / Comments
V.1	28/02/2017	Dr. Jorge Collazos (SESCAM), Dr. Beatriz Gallego (FHNP)	Final version

Executive summary

1. Description of the deliverable content, objectives and purpose

The objective of WP 8 *Activities for the exploitation, dissemination and communication of results* is to ensure the appropriate measures to exploit, disseminate and communicate the main results derived from the project development.

The deliverable 8.1 entitled as *Website and logo for Neurofibres* aims to describe the template and contents of the project website and to launch the designed logo for the project.

Acronyms

EC: European Commission

EU: European Union

WP: Working Package

PU: Public

RE: Restricted

CO: Confidential

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Website and logo for Neurofibres

NEUROFIBRES logo

The NEUROFIBRES logo will be used for all project events and activities. It is available in one version: coloured and with the acronym of the project. Furthermore, logos of the different partners can be used for activities and events in the NEUROFIBRES context.

Figure 1: NEUROFIBRES logo

NEUROFIBRES website

The NEUROFIBRES project website is conceived as an interactive platform and will be a powerful promotional tool for boosting information flow. It was created in February 2017 (month 2) and is available under the link: <http://neurofibres.eu/>. The website aims to provide access to news, updated and current events related to the development of NEUROFIBRES project and will be referred to in all NEUROFIBRES public documents.

The website targets two groups: an open public area of the website that can be accessed to by everyone, providing general information about the project; and a restricted internal area for consortium members only. The website will contain information on the following aspects:

- Public area: NEUROFIBRES project (summary and relevant information), events, partners, news, contact, publications, links.
- Password protected area: internal project documents (technical and financial reports, non-public deliverables, minutes of meetings, templates, ...)

The website will be linked to project account in Facebook and Twitter (@neurofibres). Several official Twitter accounts such as: @EU_H2020, @fet_eu, @eshorizonte2020, @HNparaplejicos, etc will be followed in order to announce 'breaking news' which clearly shows the real impact of the EU funded research (e.g. TV/radio/newspaper features).

The website will be updated and maintained regularly by SESCAM team.

Identificarse
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PROJECT

Bio-electronic microsystems hold promise for repairing the damaged central nervous system (CNS). However, this potential has not been developed because their implantation inflicts additional neural injury, and ensuing inflammation and fibrosis compromise device functionality. In Neurofibres we want to achieve a breakthrough in "Neuroregenerative Bio-electronics", developing dual-function devices that will serve as electroactive scaffolds for CNS regeneration and neural circuit activation. We engineered electroconducting microfibres (MFs) that add negligible tissue insult while promoting guided cell migration and axonal regeneration in rodents with spinal cord injury (SCI). The MFs also meet the challenge of probe miniaturisation and biofunctionalisation for ultrasensitive recording and stimulation of neural activity. An interdisciplinary consortium composed of neuroscientists, medical specialists, researchers in biomaterials, protein engineering, physics, and electrical and mechanical engineering, together with a company specialised in fabrication of microcables and microconnectors, will join efforts to design, develop, and test the MFs and complementary technology (microfibre functionalisation, assembling, and electronic interconnection), in order to produce a biologically safe and effective bio-electronic system for the treatment of SCI. This goal will be achieved through five specific objectives:

- 1) To improve the electrical conductivity, strength, and chemical stability of the microfibres.
- 2) To develop electro-responsive engineered affibodies for microfibre functionalisation.
- 3) To develop the technology for MF interconnection and assembling into implantable systems.
- 4) To perform comprehensive investigation of the immunological, glial, neuronal, and connective tissue responses to the implanted MFs and applied electrostimulation in rodent and swine SCI models.
- 5) To investigate the motor and sensory effects of microfibre implantation and electrostimulation.

Sobre nosotros

Indicamos una información resumida sobre nuestro empresa y personal: años de experiencia, especialización en el sector, trato con el cliente, etc.

Últimas noticias

- > Etiam sit amet orci eget eros faucibus tincidunt
- > Lorem ipsum dolor sit amet
- > Maecenas nisi enim mollis

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Enlaces de interés

- > Preguntas frecuentes
- > Horario de atención al público
- > Calendario de actos y eventos
- > Conozca a nuestro equipo

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Figure 2: Screenshot of NEUROFIBRES project website